

F5 APM (Access Policy Manager)

No	Specification
1.	License F5 APM
2.	Server with Resource (RAM Minimal 8 GB and vCPU minimal 4)
3.	Public IP Address
4.	Domain
5.	SSL Certificate

No	Step	Capture																										
1	Inject / Activate F5 APM License	<p>The screenshot shows the F5 APM web interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Main', 'Help', and 'About'. The 'System' menu is expanded to 'License', and the 'Summary' tab is selected. The 'General Properties' section displays the following information:</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>License Type</td> <td>Production</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Licensed Date</td> <td>Mar 8, 2025</td> </tr> <tr> <td>License Expiration Date</td> <td>Apr 23, 2025</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Active Modules</td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> APM, VE, 1 Gbps(Perpetual) (ZBFLSKG-NVMBRLE) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rate Shaping SSL, VE Max Compression, VE Exclusive Version, v12.1.X - 18.X </td> </tr> </table>	License Type	Production	Licensed Date	Mar 8, 2025	License Expiration Date	Apr 23, 2025	Active Modules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> APM, VE, 1 Gbps(Perpetual) (ZBFLSKG-NVMBRLE) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rate Shaping SSL, VE Max Compression, VE Exclusive Version, v12.1.X - 18.X 																		
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2	Import SSL Certificate for portal domain access	<p>The screenshot shows the F5 APM web interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Main', 'Help', and 'About'. The 'System' menu is expanded to 'Certificate Management', and the 'SSL Certificate List' tab is selected. The 'General Properties' section displays the following information:</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Name</td> <td>sso-binus</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Partition / Path</td> <td>Common</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Certificate Subject(s)</td> <td>sso-binus.sistemf5.com R10, Let's Encrypt</td> </tr> </table> <p>The 'Certificate Properties' section displays the following information:</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Public Key Type</td> <td>RSA</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Public Key Size</td> <td>2048 bits</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Expires</td> <td>Jun 15 2025 20:30:47 WIB</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Version</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Serial Number</td> <td>06:1d:b9:06:c1:89:d0:3a:bc:c4:ed:ab:60:c2:3e:fa:42:3f</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Fingerprint</td> <td>SHA256/1D:F4:15:EC:7C:72:64:98:93:7F:D7:03:87:E2:58:12:C4:29:10:ED:DA:3F:79:C8:C8:48:41:BC:3A:DD:7C:87</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Subject</td> <td> Common Name: sso-binus.sistemf5.com Organization: Division: Locality: State Or Province: Country: </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Issuer</td> <td> Common Name: R10 Organizational Unit: Let's Encrypt Division: Locality: State Or Province: Country: US </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Email</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Subject Alternative Name</td> <td>DNS:sso-binus.sistemf5.com</td> </tr> </table>	Name	sso-binus	Partition / Path	Common	Certificate Subject(s)	sso-binus.sistemf5.com R10, Let's Encrypt	Public Key Type	RSA	Public Key Size	2048 bits	Expires	Jun 15 2025 20:30:47 WIB	Version	3	Serial Number	06:1d:b9:06:c1:89:d0:3a:bc:c4:ed:ab:60:c2:3e:fa:42:3f	Fingerprint	SHA256/1D:F4:15:EC:7C:72:64:98:93:7F:D7:03:87:E2:58:12:C4:29:10:ED:DA:3F:79:C8:C8:48:41:BC:3A:DD:7C:87	Subject	Common Name: sso-binus.sistemf5.com Organization: Division: Locality: State Or Province: Country:	Issuer	Common Name: R10 Organizational Unit: Let's Encrypt Division: Locality: State Or Province: Country: US	Email		Subject Alternative Name	DNS:sso-binus.sistemf5.com
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3	Create Virtual Server for Publish our portal	<p>The screenshot shows the F5 APM web interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Main', 'Help', and 'About'. The 'Local Traffic' menu is expanded to 'Virtual Servers', and the 'Virtual Server List' tab is selected. The table below shows the configuration for two virtual servers:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Status</th> <th>Name</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Application</th> <th>Destination</th> <th>Service Port</th> <th>Type</th> <th>Resources</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>VS-HTTPS_SSO</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>10.0.0.15</td> <td>443 (HTTPS)</td> <td>Standard</td> <td>Edit...</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>VS-HTTP_SSO</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>10.0.0.15</td> <td>80 (HTTP)</td> <td>Standard</td> <td>Edit...</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Status	Name	Description	Application	Destination	Service Port	Type	Resources	<input type="checkbox"/>	VS-HTTPS_SSO			10.0.0.15	443 (HTTPS)	Standard	Edit...	<input type="checkbox"/>	VS-HTTP_SSO			10.0.0.15	80 (HTTP)	Standard	Edit...		
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4	SSO Create SSO Profile																													
5	Create Portal List on F5																													
6	Create SAML IDP on F5	<table border="1" data-bbox="638 772 1361 902"> <thead> <tr> <th>Name</th> <th>SAML SP Connectors</th> <th>Access Profiles</th> <th>Portal Access Resources</th> <th>Log</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Partition</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>dropbox-ldap</td> <td>Dropbox</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>From Access Profile</td> <td></td> <td>Common</td> </tr> <tr> <td>salesforce-ldap</td> <td>SalesForce</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>From Access Profile</td> <td></td> <td>Common</td> </tr> <tr> <td>zoho-ldap</td> <td>zoho</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>From Access Profile</td> <td></td> <td>Common</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Name	SAML SP Connectors	Access Profiles	Portal Access Resources	Log	Description	Partition	dropbox-ldap	Dropbox			From Access Profile		Common	salesforce-ldap	SalesForce			From Access Profile		Common	zoho-ldap	zoho			From Access Profile		Common
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7	Detail SAML IDP																													

Edit IdP Service

- General Settings
- SAML Profiles
- Endpoint Settings
- Assertion Settings**
- SAML Attributes
- Security Settings

Assertion Subject Type :
 Email Address

Assertion Subject Value*:
 %{session.logon.last.username}

Authentication Context Class Reference :
 urn:oasis:names:tc:SAML:2.0:ac:classes:PasswordProtectedTransport

Assertion Validity (in seconds) :
 600

Enable encryption of Subject

Encryption Strength :
 AES128

OK

Edit IdP Service

- General Settings
- SAML Profiles
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- Security Settings**

Signing Key :
 /Common/default.key

Signing Certificate :
 /Common/default.crt

OK Cancel

8 **Create SAML SP**

Hostname: bigip1 Date: Mar 17, 2025 User: abh
 IP Address: 10.0.0.15 Time: 11:18 PM (WIB) Role: Administrator Partition: Common

ONLINE (ACTIVE)
 Standalone

Main Help About Access >> Federation > SAML Identity Provider > External SP Connectors

SAML Service Provider SAML Identity Provider SAML Resources JSON Web Token OAuth Authorization Server OAuth Client / Resource Server PingAccess

This application is used to manage your SAML SP connectors. The BIG-IP (this device), in its role as a SAML Identity Provider, receives an authentication request from a service and in turn authenticates the user and sends an assertion back to the service. Users can create, edit and delete their SP connectors by clicking the respective buttons.

Name	SAML IdP Services	Description	Partition
Dropbox	dropbox-idp		Common
SalesForce	salesforce-idp		Common
saml_office365		Predefined SP connector object for Office 365	Common
zoho	zoho-idp		Common

9 Detail SAML (SP)

Edit SAML SP Connector

- General Settings
- Endpoint Settings
- Security Settings
- SLO Service Settings
- SP Location Settings

Service Provider Name*: /Common/Dropbox

Service Provider Entity ID*:

Service Provider Name Qualifier :

Description :

OK Cancel

Edit SAML SP Connector

- General Settings
- Endpoint Settings
- Security Settings
- SLO Service Settings
- SP Location Settings

Relay State :

Assertion Consumer Service(s)*

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Index	Default	Location URL	Binding
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	:/www.dropbox.com/saml_login	POST

OK Cancel

Edit SAML SP Connector

- General Settings
- Endpoint Settings
- Security Settings
- SLO Service Settings
- SP Location Settings

Require Signed Authentication Request

Signing Certificate*:

Response sent to SP by this device

Response must be signed Assertion must be signed

Signing Algorithm :

Assertion must be encrypted

Encryption Type :

Encryption Certificate :

OK Cancel

10	Create VPE (Visual Policy Editor) for create Flow SSO	
11	Create SMTP Client, so F5 can send OTP via Email	

Google SMTP Server

No	Step	Capture
1	Create Application Password	

Service Provider (Dropbox, Salesforce, Zoho CRM)

No	Spesifikasi
1.	Support Single Sign On via SAML Method
2.	Have ACS URL for Validation SAML Assertion
3.	Disable login direct to website

(Forcing login via SSO)

No	Step	Capture
1	Create Integration on Dropbox, Salesforce and Zoho CRM	<p>The screenshot shows the Salesforce Admin console 'Single Sign-On Settings' page. Under 'Delegated Authentication', 'Disable login with Salesforce credentials' is checked. Under 'Federated Single Sign-On Using SAML', 'SAML Enabled' is checked. 'Save' and 'Cancel' buttons are at the bottom.</p>

agility-momentum-4903.my.salesforce.com

SAML Single Sign-On Settings

Save Save & New Cancel

Name: FS API Name: FS

SAML Version: 2.0 Issuer: https://sso-bonus.system Entity ID: https://agility-momentur

Identity Provider Certificate: Choose File No file chosen Current Certificate: EMAILADDRESS=root@localhost.localdomain, CN=root@localhost.localdomain, OU=IT, O=MyCompany, L=Seattle, ST=WA, C=US Expiration: 6 Mar 2016 12:17:22 GMT

Request Signing Certificate: SelfSignedCert_09Mar2025_130531

Request Signature Method: RSA-SHA256

Assertion Decryption Certificate: Assertion not encrypted

SAML Identity Types:
 Assertion contains the User's Salesforce username
 Assertion contains the Federation ID from the User object
 Assertion contains the User ID from the User object

SAML Identity Location:
 Identity is in the NameIdentifier element of the Subject statement
 Identity is in an Attribute element

Service Provider Initiated Request Binding:
 HTTP POST
 HTTP Redirect

Identity Provider Login URL: https://sso-bonus.system/5/saml/idp/profile/redirect/post/sso

Custom Logout URL: [Empty]

Use Salesforce MFA for this SSO Provider: [1]

Single Logout Enabled: [1]

Use Selected Request Signature Method for Single Logout: [1]

Identity Provider Single Logout URL: https://130.33.49.54/saml/idp/profile/redirect/vis

Single Logout Request Binding:
 HTTP POST
 HTTP Redirect

Just-in-time User Provisioning Required Information

User Provisioning Enabled: [1]

Buttons: Save & New Cancel